

Shaping Indonesia's Energy Future: Trade-Offs Between BAU, LCD, and NDC

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- **Second NDC (2025):** Cut energy GHGs 89% by 2030 (vs. 2019 BAU), net zero by 2060, advanced economy by 2045.
- **Scenarios:** BAU, LCD, and NDC assess trade-offs in emissions, technology, and energy security.
- **LCD Pathway:** Based on the National Long-Term Development Plan, combining growth with efficiency, renewables, and coal phase-out.

Figure 1. Electricity generation by type and share of total generation in Indonesia (IEA, 2022)

- **Research Question 1:** How do annual emission limits shape Indonesia's power mix and investment compared to BAU?
- **Research Question 2:** What are the cost-emission trade-offs between BAU, LCD, and NDC pathways?

Methodology

Scenarios

Electricity Generation (PJ)

- **BAU:** Heavy reliance on coal and gas, slow renewable growth.
- **LCD:** Strong renewable expansion (solar, wind, hydro, geothermal).
- **NDC:** Moderate renewable growth; coal lingers, gas drops sharply by 2049 to meet 2050 targets.

Main Findings (2/5)

Installed Capacity (GW)

- **BAU locks in fossil capacity, with limited diversification.**
- **LCD requires a large build-out of renewables and supporting infrastructure (batteries, grid upgrades).**
- **NDC falls in between: renewables expand, but fossil fuels still have a longer role.**

Main Findings: Cost (3/5)

Investment Cost:

- BAU stays flat and lowest; NDC moderate; LCD steeply rises with big renewable investments.

Variable Cost:

- BAU cheapest; LCD highest due to storage and balancing; NDC in between.

Fixed Cost:

- BAU lowest with fossil fleet; LCD/NDC higher from diverse tech mix.

Main Findings: Cost (3/5)

Total Discounted Cost 2022-2050 (Billion USD)

Total Discounted Cost (2022–2050):

- BAU looks cheap short term but very costly long term due to fuel spending.
- LCD and NDC are cheaper overall, because renewables cut fuel and O&M costs.
- Moving from BAU to LCD/NDC saves Indonesia 59–92 B USD by 2050, while also cutting emissions. LCD savings are around 4.13% of GDP and NDC savings are 6.43% of GDP.

Main Findings (5/5)

Energy Sector Annual Emission (MTon CO₂eq)

- **Scenario outcomes:** BAU reaches >1,400 MtCO₂ by 2050; NDC lowers emissions but remains above LCD; LCD cuts deepest, nearing 350 MtCO₂ by 2050 in line with deep decarbonization.
- **Near-term trends:** 2030–2033 shows rising NDC emissions from coal and gas, while LCD advances with early wind deployment.

Invest in Clean Power

Emission limits make renewables cheaper long-term. We also can prioritize geothermal and scale up EV adoption to electrify transport.

Cost–Emission Gains

LCD/NDC save 59-92 Billion USD vs BAU while cutting emissions sharply, another way in turning climate action into an economic opportunity.

Enable the Transition

Mobilize climate finance (JETP, green bonds, PPPs) and ensure strong inter-ministerial coordination for a just, integrated pathway.

Thank you!

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Additional Findings

Transport Energy Demand from Transportation Vehicles (PJ)

- **BAU & NDC:** Transport demand grows but remains dominated by fossil fuels, with only limited uptake of electric vehicles.
- **LCD:** Policies drive rapid growth of electric motorcycles and increasing use of hydrogen buses (2045–2050), accelerating cleaner transport adoption.